

From Pixels to Semantics: Benchmarking Geospatial Foundation Model Embeddings for Vegetation Frost Damage Detection

Martin Kučera^{1,2,*}, Ondřej Lhotka^{2,3}

¹ Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic, kuceramartin@fzp.czu.cz

² Institute of Atmospheric Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

³ Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Brno, Czech Republic, ondrej.lhotka@ufa.cas.cz

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20408356

Abstract: Late frost events following anomalous warm periods pose substantial risks to Central European agriculture and forestry. The April 2024 frost in the Czech Republic caused widespread vegetation damage, yet standard optical monitoring failed to capture it due to cloud cover and subsequent vegetation recovery. This study benchmarked two Geospatial Foundation Models—AlphaEarth Foundations (AEF, 64-dimensional annual embeddings) and TESSERA (128-dimensional annual embeddings)—for detecting frost-induced vegetation anomalies across four Czech regions. AEF embeddings revealed a statistically significant anomaly gradient consistent with differential frost sensitivity: vineyards and orchards ($Z=3.07\text{--}5.16$) exhibited the strongest deviation from the 2019–2023 baseline, followed by broadleaf forests ($Z=2.83\text{--}3.89$ across regions), while coniferous forests showed variable responses. TESSERA annual embeddings detected no frost signal, attributable to their temporal invariance training objective. Complementary Sentinel-2 C_{lre} time series on paired anomalous/control sites confirmed chlorophyll depression at AEF-identified locations on the first cloud-free acquisition post-frost (29 April 2024). These findings illustrate that GFM can detect vegetation anomalies despite critical periods of obscuring cloud cover, but spectral time series remain essential for temporal attribution.

Keywords: Geospatial Foundation Models; AlphaEarth; TESSERA; frost damage; vegetation monitoring; Sentinel-2.

1 Introduction

False Spring events represent a phenological mismatch where anomalous late-winter warming triggers premature plant dehardening and budburst, exposing vulnerable tissues to subsequent hard freezes. They pose substantial risks to Central European agriculture and forestry (IPCC 2021). In April 2024, temperatures across the Czech Republic exceeded seasonal norms by 6–8 °C in late March, triggering early leaf-out, followed by severe frosts of –3 to –10 °C on April 20–22. The resulting damage to vineyards, orchards, and broadleaf forests was documented across multiple regions (CHMI 2025).

Operational vegetation monitoring relies primarily on NDVI derived from optical satellite imagery (Huang et al. 2021). For transient frost events, this approach faces two limitations: cloud cover during spring months frequently prevents image acquisition in the critical post-event window (Kumar et al. 2025) (no cloud-free Sentinel-2 scenes were available between April 11 and 26, 2024), and the mixed-pixel effect in heterogeneous landscapes dilutes

the spectral signature of localized frost damage (Cogato et al. 2020).

Geospatial Foundation Models (GFMs) compress multimodal satellite observations into dense semantic embeddings that encode landscape identity beyond individual spectral bands. AlphaEarth Foundations (AEF; Brown et al. 2025) produced 64-dimensional annual embeddings by fusing Sentinel-1/2, Landsat, GEDI LiDAR, and ERA5 climate data, projecting vectors onto the unit hypersphere S^3 . TESSERA (Feng et al. 2025) generated 128-dimensional embeddings from Sentinel-1/2 using Barlow Twins self-supervised learning, explicitly trained for temporal invariance to irregular observation schedules. Both models incorporate Sentinel-1 SAR data, rendering their embedding computation fundamentally independent of optical cloud cover.

This study addressed two questions: (1) Can annual GFM embeddings detect differential vegetation anomalies consistent with the frost sensitivity gradient across land cover types? (2) Can spectral indices provide complementary sub-annual context where annual embeddings indicate anomalies? Both GFMs were tested across four Czech regions and their sensitivity compared against Sentinel-2 spectral indices.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study areas and event

Four regions of interest (ROIs) were selected to span diverse landscapes across the Czech Republic (Table 1): R1 South Moravia (vineyards and broadleaf forests), R2 South Bohemia (conifer-dominated, bark beetle affected), R3

Table 1. Regions of interest and their characteristics.

Region	Extent (lon [°E], lat [°N])	Elev. (m)	Area (km ²)	Dominant LC
R1 S. Moravia	[15.5,48.7]–[17.5,49.8]	150–780	~22,000	Vineyards, broadleaf
R2 S. Bohemia	[13.5,48.8]–[14.5,49.3]	400–950	~5,000	Coniferous, mixed
R3 Beskids	[17.5,49.2]–[18.9,49.9]	300–1200	~9,800	Mixed
R4 C. Bohemia	[14.0,49.7]–[15.5,50.3]	180–500	~9,000	Cropland, mixed

Beskids Mountains (montane forests), and R4 Central Bohemia (agricultural lowlands). The frost event occurred on April 20–22, 2024, following temperatures 6–8 °C above seasonal norms in late March.

2.2 AlphaEarth embeddings

AlphaEarth V1 Annual embeddings (Brown et al. 2025) were accessed through Google Earth Engine (GEE). Each 10 m pixel was represented by a 64-dimensional vector on the unit hypersphere S^{63} . The GEE distribution provided already-dequantized and L2-normalized float values (verified: mean L2 norm = 0.9995). Pixels with degraded norms (< 0.9, occurring at UTM tile boundaries) were masked. Multi-tile mosaicking was applied per year.

2.3 TESSERA embeddings

TESSERA precomputed annual embeddings (Feng et al. 2025) were accessed through the geotessera Python API (128 dimensions, Euclidean space). Six analytical approaches were tested: raw cosine distance between annual embedding vectors, Mahalanobis distance using the 2019–2023 covariance matrix, year-pair drift normalization, and three hybrid variants combining these metrics. All approaches yielded consistent null results (Section 3.3).

2.4 Land cover classification

Land cover types were derived from CORINE Land Cover 2018 at 100 m resolution: broadleaf forest (class 311), coniferous forest (312), and vineyards including orchards (221 + 222). Recent forest disturbance (2020–2024) was masked using the Hansen Global Forest Change v1.11 dataset to exclude logging or natural disturbance from the analysis.

2.5 Centroid-based anomaly detection

For each land cover class and region, a historical centroid was computed as the L2-normalized mean of five baseline year embeddings (2019–2023). Annual deviation was quantified as the cosine distance between the centroid and each year's mean embedding. A Z-score was computed for the event year:

$$Z = (D^{2024} - \mu^{baseline}) / \sigma^{baseline} \quad (1)$$

where D^{2024} is the cosine distance of 2024 from the centroid, and μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of distances for 2019–2023. $Z > 1.96$ indicates deviation exceeding two standard deviations of the 2019–2023 baseline. All computations used uniform parameters: CORINE 100 m masks, 100 m analysis scale, and the same baseline period across all regions.

2.6 Sentinel-2 spectral index analysis

Sentinel-2 SR Harmonized imagery (cloud cover < 20%, Gorelick et al. 2017) was used to compute NDVI = $(B8 - B4) / (B8 + B4)$ and Chlorophyll Index Red Edge Clre = $(B8A / B5) - 1$. Regional maps were computed as the difference between May–July 2024 and 2023 median composites per land cover class at 100 m resolution. For sub-annual diagnosis, seven paired sites were selected within R1 through stratified purposive sampling. Each pair consists of

an AEF-anomalous polygon (cosine distance exceeding the 2019–2023 per-pixel maximum) and a nearby control polygon of the same land cover type, matched for elevation (± 50 m), slope, and aspect. Per-scene Clre and NDVI time series were computed for April–June 2023 and 2024.

3 Results

3.1 AlphaEarth: Z-score gradient across land cover types

AEF embeddings revealed a consistent anomaly pattern across four Czech regions in 2024 (Table 2). Vineyards and orchards were anomalous in all regions ($Z = 3.07$ – 5.16), with the strongest signal in R1 South Moravia ($Z = 5.16$, $n = 30,318$ pixels). Broadleaf forests showed significant anomalies in three of four regions ($Z = 2.83$ – 3.89), while coniferous forests exhibited variable responses—not significant in R1 ($Z = 0.85$) but strongly anomalous in R3 Beskids ($Z = 3.72$).

In R1, the Z-score gradient—vineyards (5.16) > broadleaf (2.93) > conifer (0.85)—mirrored the expected frost sensitivity ranking. Vineyards had fully developed buds by mid-April, broadleaf trees were actively leafing out, while conifers retained perennial needles. The temporal profile (Figure 1) confirmed that 2024 was uniquely anomalous for vineyards and broadleaf in R1, with coniferous forests remaining within their historical variability.

Table 2. AEF Z-scores of annual embedding deviation from the 2019–2023 baseline, by region and land cover type. Z-scores quantify deviation of the 2024 AEF annual embedding from the 2019–2023 baseline centroid (eq. 1), measured as cosine distance on S^{63} . *** $Z > 2.58$ ($p < 0.01$), ** $Z > 1.96$ ($p < 0.05$), ns = not significant ($Z \leq 1.96$). † R3 Conifer anomaly partially confounded by *Ips typographus* disturbance.

Region	Vineyards	Broadleaf	Conifer
R1 S. Moravia	5.16***	2.93***	0.85
R2 S. Bohemia	4.14***	3.03***	2.23**
R3 Beskydy	2.71***	3.89***	3.72***
R4 C. Bohemia	3.07***	0.92	1.26

Figure 1. Results of the spectral indices.

3.2 Regional variation and confounding factors

In R3 Beskids, coniferous forests showed the highest anomaly ($Z = 3.72$), attributable to ongoing spruce bark beetle (*Ips typographus*) disturbances compounding the frost effect. In R4 Central Bohemia, only vineyards were anomalous ($Z = 3.07$), lowland broadleaf forests (< 300 m)

leafed out earlier and had more frost-resistant tissues by 20 April.

3.3 TESSERA: negative result

None of six analytical approaches applied to TESSERA annual embeddings detected a frost signal. Consecutive year-pair cosine distances were indistinguishable (2023→2024: 0.283 vs. reference mean: 0.280). A built-up surface drift test confirmed that the largest inter-annual drift (0.083) coincided with the Sentinel-1B failure in December 2021, not with the 2024 frost event. The 3-day frost constituted approximately 0.8% of the annual composite window, TESSERA's Barlow Twins temporal invariance training objective explicitly suppressed sensitivity to such short-duration perturbations.

3.4 Spectral index analysis

Regional delta Clre maps (May–July 2024 minus 2023) showed positive differences for broadleaf forest and vineyards in R1 ($\Delta\text{Clre} = +0.761$ and $+0.032$, respectively).

Figure 1. Clre and NDVI time series for Pair 5 (mixed forest, R1, $\sim 48.90^\circ\text{N}$). Left panels: 2024 event year, solid red = AEF-anomalous site, solid blue = control site, grey shading = cloud gap (no Sentinel-2 acquisitions). Right panels: 2023 reference year, dashed red = AEF-anomalous site, dashed blue = control site. In 5 of 7 paired sites, the AEF-anomalous site exhibited Clre values 7–25% lower than the matched control on the first cloud-free acquisition after the frost (29 April 2024), with the divergence diminishing by mid-June as damaged vegetation recovered.

These positive values reflected compensatory vegetative growth during the warm 2024 growing season: the May–July median composite integrated recovery and post-damage regrowth alongside the initial stress period, masking the short-duration depression in late April. In contrast, coniferous forests showed a mild NDVI decline ($\Delta\text{NDVI} = -0.017$). These regional averages masked the sub-annual dynamics visible in paired-site time series. The paired-site Clre analysis (7 pairs, R1, Figure 2) provided diagnostic temporal context. In 5 of 7 pairs, AEF-anomalous sites showed Clre values 7–25% lower than their matched controls on the first cloud-free acquisition after the frost (April 29, 2024). This early-season separation diminished by mid-June as damaged vegetation recovered. In the reference year (2023), both sites within each pair tracked similar trajectories, confirming that the 2024 divergence was event specific. In the remaining two pairs, anomalous

sites exhibited higher Clre than matched controls in April–May 2024, suggesting local confounding factors such as aspect-driven microclimate differences or pre-existing within-class heterogeneity unrelated to the frost event.

4 Discussion

The Z-score gradient in R1 and R2—vineyards > broadleaf > conifer—was consistent with the frost sensitivity hypothesis. However, this gradient was not universal: in R3, coniferous forests dominated the anomaly due to bark beetle disturbance, and in R4, only vineyards were affected. The embeddings detected that 2024 deviated from the baseline but cannot attribute causality.

AEF's sensitivity likely stemmed from its multi-modal input fusion. By incorporating ERA5 climate reanalysis and GEDI structural data alongside optical and SAR observations, AEF encoded indirect stress signatures that persisted in annual aggregation. TESSERA, trained on Sentinel-1/2 with temporal invariance, was designed to produce stable embeddings regardless of observation timing—the property that ensured cloud robustness also suppressed sensitivity to events spanning < 1% of the annual window.

Both AEF and TESSERA incorporated Sentinel-1 SAR data, making their embedding computation fundamentally cloud-independent, the advantage of GFM embeddings over optical NDVI-based monitoring therefore lies not in SAR inclusion per se, but in the semantic compression of a full multi-modal annual time series into a landscape-state vector. Regarding GEDI's role: its extremely sparse spatio-temporal sampling (quasi-random transects, revisit intervals exceeding two months at Central European latitudes) makes it unlikely to contribute meaningfully to detecting the three-day April 2024 frost perturbation. GEDI's value in AEF lies primarily in encoding structural canopy baseline information for the annual embedding rather than resolving short-duration phenological anomalies.

The spectral analysis complemented the embedding results. Annual embeddings and sub-annual indices addressed different questions: embeddings integrated the full-year trajectory including recovery dynamics, while indices captured instantaneous biophysical state. The paired-site Clre time series demonstrated that AEF-identified anomalies corresponded to locations with early-season chlorophyll depression: in 5 of 7 pairs, anomalous sites exhibited Clre values 7–25% lower than matched controls on 29 April 2024, with the divergence diminishing by mid-June as damaged vegetation recovered. This temporal specificity was absent from annual embeddings, which integrated the full growing season including post-damage recovery. This complementarity suggests an operational workflow where GFM embeddings serve as spatially explicit anomaly detectors and targeted spectral time series provide causal diagnosis. In two non-confirming pairs, anomalous sites exhibited higher Clre than controls, indicating that AEF detected landscape-level deviation irrespective of cause, spectral evidence remained necessary for attribution.

A sensitivity analysis using hybrid masks (ESA WorldCover 10 m intersected with CORINE) preserved the same Z-score rank order (R1: vineyards 3.92, broadleaf 2.83, conifer 1.94), confirming that the gradient was not a land cover classification artifact.

Several limitations applied. No field-based ground truth was available for direct validation. The annual temporal resolution diluted a 3-day event, yielding small absolute cosine distances (0.01–0.05). The analysis could not separate frost from other 2024-specific stressors. The paired-site selection was guided by AEF anomaly magnitude, consequently, the Clre time series confirmed physiological deviation at AEF-identified locations but could not serve as an independent validation of AEF detection sensitivity. Future work should prioritize sub-annual TESSERA inference to achieve temporal resolution sufficient for causal attribution. Additionally, expressing spectral time series x-axes as accumulated growing degree-days (base 0°C) rather than calendar date would normalize for inter-annual thermal variability and improve cross-year and cross-site comparability of phenological responses.

5 Conclusions

AEF annual embeddings detected statistically significant differential anomalies in 2024 consistent with the ecological frost sensitivity gradient. Vineyards showed the strongest anomaly across all four regions ($Z = 3.07\text{--}5.16$). TESSERA annual embeddings did not detect the event due to their temporal invariance objective. Sentinel-2 Clre time series on AEF-identified sites confirmed early-season chlorophyll depression in 5 of 7 paired comparisons. GFM embeddings can serve as cloud-independent anomaly detectors, while causal attribution requires sub-annual spectral or embedding data.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Czech Science Foundation (GA ČR), grant No. 26-22280S “Emerging off-season heat waves in Europe”.

6 References

Brown, C.F., Brumby, S.P., Guzder-Williams, B., Vance, T., Lewis, S.L., Taneja, J., Hancher, M., Bhatt, U., Goldblatt, C., Fields, E., Pifer, A., Slaughter, R., Kwan, C., 2025. AlphaEarth Foundations: An embedding field model for

accurate and efficient global mapping from sparse label data. arXiv preprint arXiv:2507.22291.

CHMI, 2025. Klimatologická ročenka České republiky 2024 [Climatological Yearbook of the Czech Republic 2024]. Czech Hydrometeorological Institute, Prague. ISBN 978-80-7653-083-6.

Cogato, A., Meggio, F., Collins, C., Marinello, F., 2020. Medium-resolution multispectral data from Sentinel-2 to assess the damage and the recovery time of late frost on vineyards. *Remote Sensing* 12 (11), 1896.

EEA, 2018. Copernicus CORINE Land Cover 2018. European Environment Agency, Copenhagen. <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover/clc2018>. (Accessed 1 April 2026).

Feng, Z., Sherrah, J., Stefanidis, A., Anil, R., 2025. TESSERA: Temporal embeddings of surface spectra for earth representation and analysis. arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.20380.

Gorelick, N., Hancher, M., Dixon, M., Ilyushchenko, I., Thau, D., Moore, R., 2017. Google Earth Engine: Planetary-scale geospatial analysis for everyone. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 202, 18–27.

Hansen, M.C., Potapov, P.V., Moore, R., Hancher, M., Turubanova, S.A., Tyukavina, A., Thau, D., Stehman, S.V., Goetz, S.J., Loveland, T.R., Kommareddy, A., Egorov, A., Chini, L., Justice, C.O., Townshend, J.R.G., 2013. High-resolution global maps of 21st-century forest cover change. *Science* 342 (6160), 850–853.

Huang, S., Tang, L., Hupy, J.P., Wang, Y., Shao, G., 2021. A commentary review on the use of normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) in the era of popular remote sensing. *Journal of Forestry Research* 32 (1), 1–6.

IPCC, 2021. Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Kumar, S., Ghosh, S.S., Mandal, D., Bhattacharya, A., Porwal, A., Karthikeyan, L., 2025. Enhancing vegetation monitoring: a proposal for a Sentinel-2 based vegetation health index. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing* 6, 1581355.

Zanaga, D., Van De Kerchove, R., Daems, D., De Keersmaecker, W., Brockmann, C., Kirches, G., Wevers, J., Cartus, O., Santoro, M., Fritz, S., Lesiv, M., Herold, M., Tsensbazar, N.E., Xu, P., Ramoino, F., Arino, O., 2022. ESA WorldCover 10 m 2021 v200. Zenodo.